

NASA'S LASER RISK REDUCTION PROGRAM: A RISK REDUCTION APPROACH FOR TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT

Eduardo Torres-Martinez¹

William S. Heaps²

Upendra N. Singh³

¹ NASA Goddard Space Flight Ctr., Earth Science Technology Office, Greenbelt MD 20771

² NASA Goddard Space Flight Ctr., Laser and Electro-optics Branch, Greenbelt MD 20771

³ NASA Langley Research Ctr., Systems Engineering Competency, Hampton VA 23681

ABSTRACT

The benefits of Earth Science (ES) laser instrumentation have been proven by decades of earth-science observations. Lasers allow remote sensing of earth-system variables such as sea elevation, atmospheric composition, wind profiles, cloud cover, ice mass, and vegetation canopy. Further, orbiting platforms provide a unique vantage point that allows laser measurements on a global scale. NASA implemented the Laser Risk Reduction Program (LRRP) to identify and address capability-gap areas where new devices or processes could yield high-reliability mission-ready parts, and to develop components needed to advance the state-of-the-art of laser-based instrumentation.

This paper discusses LRRP's approach and the evolution of the program's developments from inception to their planned infusion into NASA's missions. It is the first part of a three-paper presentation (Program goals and organization; 1 μ developments and results at the Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC); and 2 μ developments and results at Langley Research Center (LaRC)) that summarizes LRRP's goals, formulation approach, management organization, and final results.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of light detection and ranging (lidar) techniques for NASA observations was the logical next step beyond traditional passive (e.g. radiometers and spectrometers) and active (e.g. radar) remote sensing techniques. Lidar allows day and night observations and affords better spatial resolution while using smaller apertures than radar instrumentation [1]. Also, the shorter wavelengths of laser light enable

detection of molecules and aerosol particles. For these reasons, almost half of the measurements identified by the National Academies recommendation to NASA will be performed by laser-based systems, and will require new components for an advanced generation of laser instrumentation.

Developing space-qualified laser components is extremely challenging because commercially available devices – the precursors to high-reliability flight parts – are designed and manufactured for terrestrial uses where lifetime and reliability concerns are minimal. Clearly, effective mitigation of development risks dictated a systematic study of existing laser architectures and components, and a well-focused development program.

In the 1990s several lidar missions (i.e. MOLA I, LITE, MOLA II, VCL, and SPARCLE) had technical problems that led to concerns about the readiness of laser technologies for space applications. In response, NASA convened an external review panel to assess the situation and make recommendations for a program that would reduce the risk of future laser-based missions. Based on the panel's findings and recommendations, a plan was formulated for a program that would leverage NASA's expertise on 1 μ and 2 μ lasers (at GSFC and LaRC respectively) with collaborations with industry and academia partners.

The program was approved by NASA's administrator in FY02 and was funded for a five year duration by a partnership between the Science Mission Directorate (SMD) and Exploration Systems Mission Directorate (ESMD) [2].

2. THE LRRP APPROACH

LRRP sought to reduce risk by investigating the root causes of failures in laser systems for space and using

Table 1 - Four lidar techniques enable diverse applications

LIDAR TYPE	MEASURES	EARTH SCIENCE APPLICATIONS	SPACE EXPLORATION APPLICATIONS
Doppler	Velocity	Wind Fields River/Ocean Flows	Planetology Navigation Operations Landing Wind Profiles
Altimetry	Distance	Ice Sheet Mass Vegetation Canopy Land Topography	Planetology Navigation Operations Landing Hazard-Detection
Differential Absorption	Concentration	Ozone Carbon Dioxide	Planetology
Backscatter	Density	Cloud Properties Aerosol Density	Planetology Navigation Operations

the knowledge gained to develop reliable laser architectures and components to meet the requirements of future instrument systems. Consequently, its focus was to develop and demonstrate laser technologies to the point where they could be deployed with confidence on new missions. To maximize return on investment, focus was placed on enabling developments for four basic measurement techniques (i.e. ranging, Doppler, differential absorption, and backscattering) used to perform high-priority earth-science measurements. For these techniques, crucial technology gaps were identified in the areas of 1) laser transmitters, 2) pump laser diodes, 3) frequency conversion, and 4) lidar receivers and detectors.

The risk reduction goal of LRRP required that research be conducted in non-traditional technology development areas to advance the readiness of devices for space applications (e.g. improve commercial design and manufacturing practices to resolve diode lifetime issues). Additionally, advanced materials research would be conducted to improve the performance of lidar components such as transmitters and receivers/detectors. These research activities would support development of space-qualified laser components, investigate component reliability issues and failure modes, and support development of ancillary devices and subsystems for lidar systems.

Table 2 - SMD missions enabled by LRRP technologies

MISSION	MEASUREMENT APPLICATIONS
ICESat-II	Laser altimeter
DESDynI	Laser altimeter, Vegetation lidar
ASCENDS	Multi-frequency laser
ACE	Backscatter lidar
LIST	Laser altimeter
GRACE II	Laser ranging
3D-WINDS	Doppler lidar

Table 3 - Task similarities for 1 and 2 micron systems

TASK CATEGORY	RISK REDUCTION AREA	GSFC 1μ	LaRC 2μ
Pulsed laser	Laser rods; Amplifiers; Beam Quality; Efficiency; Reliability/Lifetime	√	√
Laser-diode arrays (pump)	Architecture; Fabrication Materials; Packaging; Reliability/Lifetime; Space Qualification; Commercial Availability	√	√
Wavelength conversion to UV	Efficiency; Amplifiers; Optical Damage Control; Efficiency; Reliability/Lifetime	√	√
2 μ Direct detector (low noise)	Responsivity; Noise performance; Active Area		√
2 μ Coherent receiver	Quantum efficiency; Packaging		√

3. LIDAR APPLICATIONS

Although it was initially envisioned to apply the four lidar techniques to high-priority ES applications (see Table 1), these techniques enable fundamental measurements that also find use in space-borne exploration activities. The cross-cutting potential of the program’s charter was recognized during LRRP formulation, and a portion of the program’s funding was provided in FY02 by ESMD’s Code R “Enabling Concepts and Technology Program” to pursue those developments. In FY05, funding support was continued by ESMD under the “Laser/lidar Technologies for Exploration” program.

It is noteworthy that the initial strategy of focusing technology developments on advanced instrument capabilities served SMD well, because seven of the ES complement of applications proposed by the National Research Council’s (NRC) Decadal Survey Missions in 2007 will require laser-based instrumentation (see Table 2). We already know that these missions require state-of-the-art instrumentation, and some demand advanced accuracy and resolution capabilities (e.g. ASCENDS’ 1.0 ppB CO2 measurement precision) that will be extremely challenging to meet. For missions in Table 2, infusion paths are already established for key LRRP technologies.

4. DEVELOPMENT TASKS

Selection of tasks for LRRP’s first year was primarily dictated by ongoing laser technology work and the timing of the fiscal-year funding cycle. After identifying existing work to be funded, additional LRRP tasks were chosen by a competitive selection

Figure 1 - LRRP roadmap shows how laser technologies and subsystems combine to enable measurements.

method, whereby GSFC and LaRC laser technologists submitted proposals (1 ~ 2 pages) describing the problem they would work on, the approach to solving the problem, schedule and delivery milestones, and a task budget [3]. From these proposals a full suite of tasks addressing primary technology needs were selected and funded.

As Table 3 illustrates, the majority of tasks for both GSFC and LaRC were centered on development of pulsed-laser components, improvement of laser-diode pump efficiency and reliability, and development of components for wavelength conversion to UV. Certain development tasks were not duplicated because, in some cases, suitable components (e.g. a 1 μ low-noise photon detector) were already available for space.

5. ROADMAPMING THE WAY

To integrate tasks within the program and to understand the relative priority of developments ‘technology roadmaps’ were generated by the GSFC and LaRC development teams. These roadmaps graphically depicted the inter-relationships of developments, and most importantly, how end-

products would ultimately come together to implement instrument solutions. Also, these roadmaps were very useful to track the termination and startup of tasks that invariably occurred as work progressed and the program evolved.

At the program level, Figure 1 depicts how LRRP technologies being developed at GSFC and LaRC will combine with additional subsystems to implement new laser instrumentation for NASA’s research and exploration activities. Not shown in the graphic are many possible applications for other U.S. federal agencies such as the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, the Department of Defense, the Environmental Protection Agency, the Department of Homeland Security, and others.

When used as a portfolio-analysis tool, this roadmap also helps visualize two features of LRRP’s technology portfolio: 1) the similarity of development efforts (at 1 μ and 2 μ wavelengths) in which several approaches employ similar functional blocks to perform different measurements; and 2) the need to develop ‘technology packages’ that associate all the technology deliverables needed to perform one measurement type (e.g. a laser rod, an amplifier, and a detector). This logical association is an essential

element of portfolio management, for it ensures that inter-dependent technologies remain in lockstep as they move through the technology pipeline so they are delivered concurrently.

6. PROGRAM RESULTS

Performance of a technology program is primarily measured by its infusion rate, that is, the proportion of technologies adopted vs. the total initially funded. In this regard, the LRRP has done very well. The NRC has endorsed several missions involving laser-based instruments for space-borne remote sensing and LRRP technologies are immediately applicable to all the proposed measurements.

In many cases though, infusion rate alone does not tell the whole story because not all funded work yields technology deliverables. For instance, some LRRP tasks funded basic research activities (e.g. to find new laser rod and detector material formulations) to develop knowledge that would enable mechanization of new technologies. Other tasks funded studies (e.g. pump-diode lifetime testing) that provided data needed to ascertain the operational lifetime (i.e. reliability) of components. Although these tasks did not deliver infusible products, they do not represent sunk costs because it is these low-TRL activities that provide the foundation for subsequent technology developments.

LRRP was funded for a five-year period to accelerate development of crucial laser technologies. After the end of the program's funding, several LRRP technologists have successfully transitioned their developments from directed funding to competed funding sources. For instance, LaRC's 2 μ laser technologies are being applied in a coherent-detection approach to demonstrate a tropospheric wind-measurement instrument prototype (a 2007 IIP award). This instrument is scheduled to take part in SMD's Genesis and Rapid Intensification Processes (GRIP) airborne campaign this summer. This prototype is a scaled precursor for what could later become the instrument flown on the "3D-Winds" decadal survey mission.

7. CONCLUSION

Based on prior experiences with laser-based instrumentation and concerns about perceived risks to future space-based lidar investigations, NASA commissioned an external review panel to address the

situation. This panel made recommendations which NASA implemented through the LRRP. Collaboration between GSFC, LaRC, industry, and academia were fruitful and LRRP activities have delivered valuable technologies to SMD. By retiring or mitigating key technology gaps in ES laser instrumentation, LRRP technologists have fulfilled the Program's goal of reducing risk for NASA's laser-enabled decadal missions.

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9. REFERENCES

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